

PSYCHOLOGICAL BARRIERS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article presents the consideration of the types of psychological barriers in the process of learning a foreign language. Foreign language learning. The factors of occurrence of this phenomenon are outlined, as well as the possible technologies of overcoming psychological barriers in the process of learning a foreign language.*

Keywords: *Psychological barrier, foreign language, learning process, personality-oriented approach, teacher, student, learning motivation.*

Globalization is an integral part of our lives. Therefore, today the relevance of learning foreign languages, in particular English, is beyond doubt, as interest in foreign culture, education, travel, life and work abroad is increasing. It is known that English is the most widespread international means of communication (including information technologies and web space), for the majority of the population it is a native or state language. This is due to historical, political and geographical background, as well as socio-economic and cultural development.

Proficiency in English offers great prospects for those who know it, but not every person chooses a linguistic field of study when entering a higher education institution. Mastering English is a labor-intensive process. In non-linguistic universities one of the main problems for students is the so-called language anxiety and psychological barriers, especially for those students for whom English is not a major subject or future activity. The overcoming of language anxiety and psychological barriers continues to be a topical issue in educational psychology and the educational process of higher education institutions.

In order to determine the content of linguistic anxiety, it is necessary to find out the meaning of the term, to identify the features, signs of the concept. "Anxiety is a relatively stable property of personality, characterizing the predisposition to perceive a fairly wide range of situations as threatening and react to them, as a rule, by developing feelings of anxiety, worry" [1]. Language Anxiety - Language Anxiety is a property of a person learning a foreign language, which is expressed in the

difficulties of foreign communication, fear of negative evaluations of other interlocutors involved, inflated requirements for themselves and the desired result.

Language anxiety is a kind of psychological barrier, respectively, overcoming barriers will get rid of language anxiety. The fear of being evaluated is one of the strongest fears, which is deformed into language anxiety. Emotional reactions to subjective opinion form the learner's self-esteem (positive or negative). "An emotionally prosperous student fully experiences his own success, adequately and balanced attitude to possible failures" [2]. Positive (encouraging) opinion/evaluation favorably affects the level of assessment of own abilities, negative - leads to the emergence of complexes.

Learning foreign languages is conditioned by many psychological factors: flexibility, learning ability, emotional stability, as well as the ability to psychologically engage in the learning process. In the learning process. The effectiveness of such a multifaceted process of foreign language acquisition is directly related to the psychological readiness of the learner to learn and use a foreign language both at lessons and in life situation, to believe in his/her abilities, not to be afraid to make mistakes, i.e. to be able to overcome psychological barriers. To overcome psychological barriers. The process of mastering a foreign language directly depends on the psychological state of the student. It includes psychological readiness to overcome language barriers. In many sources, a psychological barrier is considered as a relatively stable state that manifests itself in passivity. State, which manifests itself in passivity of an individual, suppressing his/her activity and serving as an obstacle to successful and effective achievement of the set goals. An obstacle to successful and effective achievement of the set goals.

Foreign scientists, studying this phenomenon, distinguish the following types of psychological barriers. The following types of psychological barriers are distinguished when studying this phenomenon: insecurity, fear of new vocabulary, sudden speech, emotional state of the student, fear of failure, memory capacity of new vocabulary, sudden speech, emotional state of the student, fear of failure, memory capacity [3]. Barriers arising in the learning process can be grouped by the reason of their occurrence into psychophysiological, informational, evaluative, intracultural and semantic. Psychophysiological barrier arises due to the violation of contact between teacher and student. Informational barriers are characterized by incorrectly selected curricula and methods, inconsistency in the level of educational materials. Evaluation barriers are caused by biased assessment of one's activity, negative attitude of the teacher, which affects the result of evaluation. Meaning and intercultural barriers are related to the inability to communicate in a foreign language,

the inability to communicate in a foreign language. Communication in a foreign language, unwillingness of the learner to take into account cultural traditions, to study the linguistic peculiarities of other nations. An indicator of effective learning activity is the ability to overcome barriers. For this purpose, students should have a sufficient level of learning motivation and healthy self-esteem. Most linguists and psychologists consider motivation to be one of the main factors without which even the most gifted people cannot achieve their goals. The motivation of a person learning a foreign language consists of effort and emotion [4].

In general, the technology of overcoming psychological barriers is a system of methods and means determining the nature of pedagogical influence on mental spheres and means, determining the nature of pedagogical impact on the mental spheres of the student's individuality. It contains the following stages: diagnostic (diagnostics of the levels of individuality spheres and language skills), target (objectives of overcoming the barriers), content (system of tasks, exercises, monitoring of achieved results) [5]. It is possible to get rid of psychological barriers by creating situations close to real life. They motivate students to be creative and to search for independent solutions, it is important for the teacher to create a comfortable psychological atmosphere in which the abilities and inner capabilities of students will be the students' abilities and inner capabilities will be developed.

The connection with life and emotional coloring allows students to feel safe, which encourages them to express themselves freely in foreign language lessons. Expression of their opinions in foreign language lessons. The use of games, discussions, problem questions and situations in the process of lessons involves students in the learning process. In the process of overcoming psychological barriers, the teacher should apply a person-centered approach [6]. Personality-oriented approach is used to develop and support each student's interest in learning foreign languages. The teacher should go beyond the traditional system of teaching, to allow students to participate in collective creative activity. Ultimately, this will help to overcome isolation, increase communicative skills, bring to the forefront the understanding and ability to use the skills acquired in the process of learning in everyday life and create motivation for learning a foreign language.

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